

WorldCOM deliverable D-JRP13-WP3.1&2: Lateral flow test for on-site use together with Smartphone App for collection of data and transmission of test results to reference laboratory.

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Important disclaimer: this task now relies on colorimetric LAMP rather than lateral flow results to test for the presence of target AMR genes from samples obtained on-site.

Loop-mediated isothermal amplification (LAMP) technology is a relatively low-cost technique with portable instrumentation for rapid molecular detection of microbial pathogens and antimicrobial resistance (AMR); however, there is a need for on-site mobile communication to automate data analysis and detection. To reduce user subjectivity when interpreting these results and for data curation purposes, we have developed a novel smartphone application that automates a large part of this effort.

Colorimetric LAMP assays targeting key extended spectrum beta-lactamases genes: *bla_{KPC}*, *bla_{OXA-48}*, *bla_{OXA-23}*, *bla_{VIM}* and colistin resistance gene *mcr-1* were tested using pig faecal samples. Spiked and un-spiked samples were processed for the detection of these AMR genes and the LAMP results were imaged using a mobile phone for data analysis, processing, and communication. An application on the Android platform, or smart app, was developed to automate this process and communicate with the cloud-hosted database 'Firebase' for data curation.

The user interaction and experience (UIX) for this smart app was developed with Python using an open-source, cross-platform package called 'Kivy', and tested on a mobile Samsung S10 device. With respect to the application backend, an image processing and computer vision library called 'OpenCV-Python' was used for pattern recognition. The key processing steps performed by the backend are summarised as follows: first, a captured image of a colorimetric LAMP assay is transformed into an HSV colour space, followed by thresholding and contour edge detection, to extract candidate regions of interest (i.e., pink/yellow regions). Subsequently, a hierarchical clustering technique is used to localise the region of the image where the LAMP assay is present; this step proved necessary for processing samples captured in outdoor settings with non-uniform backgrounds. The last step utilises a machine learning method: 'nearest centroid classifier' to make positive/negative predictions for the test samples according to the test controls. Throughout this process the user is guided by following a series of confirmatory steps with a minimalist design to avoid digital clutter.

This mobile smart app satisfies a key part of this deliverable: 'transmission of test results to a reference laboratory', by collecting metadata input by the user (e.g., targeted genes) and offering the option of uploading this, together with the original and annotated images, to a cloud-hosted database called Firebase. This storage solution is secured by requiring user authentication using email and password for online access.

Outdoor field tests were conducted to validate the predictive accuracy of this mobile smart app. With respect to the experimental design, LAMP assays successfully detected target AMR markers in tested spiked and un-spiked pig faecal samples. The smart app acquired images of these LAMP assays and successfully detected colour changes of all the assay tubes over a variety of background conditions. Subsequently, the images were annotated with the result predictions and uploaded to the database for future reference.

An on-site and mobile LAMP assay for the detection of AMR genes in pig faeces, combined with automated processing and communication of results using a smart app has been developed. The smart app assists with data curation and alleviates user burden when working on-site in potentially challenging conditions, thereby streamlining data analysis.